

Complex Formation with some Bidentate Ligands. I. Solution Equilibria in the Complex Formation of Bivalent Metal Ions with some *vic*-Hydroxy Aldehydes

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The proton-ligand stability constants of salicylaldehyde, 3-methylsalicylaldehyde, 4-methylsalicylaldehyde, 5-methylsalicylaldehyde and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, and stability constants of their complexes with Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Mg^{2+} have been determined in ethanol-water medium (50% v/v) at $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO_4) and 25° by the Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The order of the stability constants has been found to be $\text{Cu} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Mn} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Mg}$, which is in agreement with the Irving-Williams order of stability of bivalent metal complexes.

MUCH work has been so far done on isolation of solid complexes of *vic*-hydroxy aldehydes and their derivatives and their characterisation. Equally important contributions are expected for complex formation in solutions. *vic*-Hydroxy aldehydes give interesting analytical reagents like oximes, thiosemicarbazones, semicarbazones, and versatile ligands like Schiff bases and anils. Present series aims at a detailed comparative study of these ligands.

Salicylaldehyde (SA), 3-methylsalicylaldehyde (3-MSA), 4-methylsalicylaldehyde (4-MSA), 5-methylsalicylaldehyde (5-MSA) and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (5-BSA) from chelates with many metals. The present paper deals with the formation constants of the complexes of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Mg^{2+} with SA, 3-MSA, 5-MSA and 5-BSA using Calvin-Bjerrum technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The studies were carried out in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO_4) at $25^\circ (\pm 0.1^\circ)$.

Experimental

Potentiometric titrations were carried out by using Radiometer M-4 pH meter (calibrated with phthalate buffer). The readings of pH meter in 50% ethanol were corrected for solvent effect as previously reported¹⁻³.

Salicylaldehyde (AnalaR) was used as such. Other *vic*-hydroxy aldehydes were prepared by using standard procedures^{4,5}. Carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (AnalaR) solution (0.98 M) was prepared according to the method of Serjeant⁶. Solutions of the ligands (0.04 M) were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of the compound in ethanol. Metal perchlorate solutions were prepared by treating 2 M HClO_4 (20 ml) with excess of the oxide or carbonate of A.R. grade and suitably diluting the resulting neutral solutions to 100 ml of 0.2 M (approximately). The metal contents were determined by standard procedures⁷.

Titration procedure: Following solutions were titrated against standard sodium hydroxide (0.98 M) free from CO_2 : (i) 4 ml 0.2 M HClO_4 + 0.78 ml 4 M NaClO_4 + 20 ml ethanol + 15.22 ml distilled water, (ii) 4 ml 0.2 M HClO_4 + 0.78 ml 4 M NaClO_4 + 10 ml 0.04 M reagent + 10 ml ethanol + 15.22 ml distilled water and (iii) 2 ml 0.2 M HClO_4 + 2 ml 0.02 M metal perchlorate solution containing 0.2 M HClO_4 + 0.77 ml 4 M NaClO_4 + 10 ml 0.4 M reagent + 10 ml ethanol + 15.23 ml distilled water.

Results and Discussion

Salicylaldehyde, a representative *vic*-hydroxy aromatic aldehyde possesses favourable features for the formation of a stable five-membered chelate

ring with metal ions. The proton-ligand stability constants and the metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by using half-integral and graphical methods. The pK values of methyl substituted salicylaldehydes and 5-BSA are in the order, 4-MSA > 3-MSA > 5-MSA > SA > 5-BSA. Because of methyl group, there will be higher electron density around carbonyl oxygen compared with that of SA. Hence, there will be stronger hydrogen bond formation with C=O and hence phenolic proton will have higher ionisation energy⁹. The CH_3 group has positive inductive effect (+1) and there is increase in electron density at the oxygen atom of C=O group. This facilitates the formation of stronger hydrogen bonding as compared to SA. Increased hydrogen bonding hampers the ionisation of phenolic OH and leads to higher pK value. In 5-MSA, the methyl group is in *para* position to the OH group, and the former can donate electrons easily to the latter *via* hyper-conjugation making 5-MSA more difficult to ionise as compared to SA. 4-MSA shows a very high pK value. The plot of Hammett σ^- values for the methyl substituent in *ortho*, *meta* and *para* positions to OH group against pK values gives a straight line plot. However, 4-MSA shows a deviation. The three of them decidedly have higher $\log K_1^H$ values as the effect of the CH_3 -substituent. The behaviour of the substituent in *ortho* position is somewhat anomalous⁹⁻¹¹. The proton-ligand stability constants are fairly in agreement with calculated values (except 4-MSA).

Electron repelling character of the substituents group is in increasing order, $\text{Br} > \text{H} > m\text{-CH}_3 > o\text{-CH}_3 > p\text{-CH}_3$. However, the pK values do not follow this order strictly and the *o*- and *m*- CH_3 substituents show strong difference from expected order.

The observed orders for the five ligands are SA, $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Mn} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Mg}$; 3-MSA, $\text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Mn} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Mg}$; 4-MSA, $\text{Cu} > \text{Mn} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Mg}$; 5-MSA, $\text{Cu} > \text{Co} > \text{Mn} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Mg}$; 5-BSA, $\text{Ni} > \text{Mn} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd}$. This is in agreement with earlier reports^{9,12-14}.

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND SYSTEMS OF SA AND ITS SUBSTITUTED DERIVATIVES

Cations	Constant	SA	3-MSA	4-MSA	5-MSA	5-BSA
H^+	$-\log K_{OH}^H$	9.05	10.40	12.25	9.55	8.2
Cu^{++}	$-\log K_1$	6.60	—	9.11	7.23	—
Co^{++}	$-\log K_1$	—	5.86	—	6.04	—
Ni^{++}	$-\log K_1$	5.90	5.66	—	—	5.90
Mn^{++}	$-\log K_1$	5.32	5.09	8.14	5.35	5.53
Zn^{++}	$-\log K_1$	5.10	5.01	7.92	5.16	5.24
Cd^{++}	$-\log K_1$	4.37	3.96	6.66	4.35	4.41
Mg^{++}	$-\log K_1$	3.18	2.82	3.88	3.15	—

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References

- B. GUTBEZAHL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 565.
- R. G. BATES and G. SCHWARZENBACH, *Helv. Chim. Acta* 1955, 38, 699.
- R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH", John Wiley, New York, 1954, p 223.
- J. C. DUFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 547.
- C. M. BREWSTER and L. H. MILLAM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 763.
- E. P. SERJEANT and A. ALBERT, "Determination of Ionisations Constants", 2nd. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1971.
- A. I. VOGEL, "The Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1961.
- S. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, 16, 88.
- K. E. JABALPURWALA, K. A. VENKATACHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1027.
- C. JR. POSTMUS, A. K. IRVING, C. A. CRAIG and R. S. MATTHEWIS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 2693.
- P. V. KAMAT, N. B. LAXMESHWAR and M. G. DATAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 345.
- H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAM, *Nature (London)*, 1948, 162, 746.
- L. E. MALEY and D. P. MELLOR, *Nature (London)*, 1948, 161, 346.
- R. G. PEARSON and F. BASOLO, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions - Study of Complexes in Solution", John Wiley, New York, 1958, p. 16.
- H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.